

LIMITED LIABILITY OF THE FOUNDER OF A LIMITED LIABILITY COMPANY IN THE FORM OF AN INDIVIDUAL LEGAL ENTITY AS THE SOLE MANAGEMENT IN AN INDIVIDUAL COMPANY

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Abstract

Man in his life always needs another human being, with the meaning that man must always be able to live in society. In society, it often operates a business, which of course is shaded by a law, namely the law of business. Basically there are legal subjects consisting of individuals or individuals and legal entities. One of the business organizations that are often established by the community is a limited liability company. Where the company will be established by an agreement between two or more persons. The liability given to the parties in a limited liability company is of a limited nature, but in certain events and times the liability of a limited nature may be lost or even simply erased.

Keywords: Individual, Business, Limited Liability Company

A. INTRODUCTION

Indonesia is a country based on law. All behaviors and actions carried out are always accompanied by laws and all applicable regulations. In a country and in the life of a certain society there is a legal science that applies in it, this legal science is called positive science.

The law that is being applied in the Indonesian state until now is a form of positive law in which there are regulations regarding the life of the Indonesian people. Positive law (Indonesia) is all principles and the whole rule that has regulations regarding a human relationship in a society (Arief, 2016: 4).

In English, the legal term is "law", then the word "droit" is a legal term derived from French, then the term "recht" is a legal term taken in Dutch, and with the same term, namely "recht" which is the legal language obtained from German. Meanwhile, other legal terms that are adapted from other countries such as Arabic, namely the word "sharia" (Arief, 2016: 9).

In a law, there are various elements that must always be fulfilled, including the

- a. Regulations governing human behavior towards associations found in a society;
- b. The regulation is an existing regulation because of the bodies, the authorities that administer it.
- c. Existing regulations are coercive regulations; and

- d. The sanctions set for violations of these regulations have a firm nature (Arief, 2016: 10).

The presence of a law in general certainly contains several functions in it, where these functions consist of:

- a. In a society the law functions like a tool of order and order. In this case, the law is a forum for guidelines as a guide for humans in behavior. That way public awareness is needed to respond that in a law there are orders and prohibitions that need to be considered. So that this can realize the function of law, namely as a tool of order in society.
- b. In the case of inner-born social justice, the function of the law here is that the law is present as a means for justice to be realized. With the nature of the law that is coercive, binding, imposed by the tools of the state who have the authority, and this causes fear for people to do something that can cause violations of the law, because sanctions will be imposed as part of the threat to its violators. Thus will be the attainment of a justice.
- c. Due to its nature as a binding and coercive force, a law can function as a driving force in development activities. So that it can be useful as a tool of authority so that society can be directed in a more advanced direction (Arief, 2016: 11-12).

Basically, the legal system is certainly present in every country. The legal system is the national legal system of each country. The legal system is a unit of legal regulations which in this case are divided into several parts that have relationships or relationships between one another, which are then systematically arranged in such a way according to their principles, with a function for the existence of goals that can be achieved. Each of these legal regulations has a relationship between each other as a whole (Wagiman, 2022: 24).

The legal system that applies to countries in the world generally consists of two forms of legal systems, which consist of common law and civil law. Where these two legal systems have differences in characteristics between them, where the common law system is a legal system in which in its application the source of law is not written, in this case derived from the decisions of previous judges is more dominating. Meanwhile, civil law is a legal system whose application is more dominated by written law (Wagiman, 2022: 26).

Another striking difference found in the common law and civil law legal systems is the separation of public law and private law. Where in common law public law and private law are separated clearly and unequivocally, while in civil law the separation between the two laws is not clearly and unequivocally detailed (Wagiman, 2022:26).

Meanwhile, in Indonesia, the prevailing legal system is a legal system with a combination of several laws. These laws include customary law, religious law, and law in European countries, especially the Netherlands, which is a country that once colonized Indonesia.

The Presence of the Dutch to colonize Indonesia was for 3.5 (three point five) centuries or 350 (three hundred and fifty) years. With the long Presence of the Dutch in Indonesia, there are many relics, including one of which is the legal system. Thus it can be said that the laws applied

in Indonesia are almost entirely of Dutch origin. In other words, it is said that Indonesian law is a law that still refers to the law created by the Dutch.

B. RESEARCH METHOD

The research method is a stage to answer the question of how to make a study can be realized. In its discussion, the research method discusses the implementation of the research reviewed through its procedures. The way of working that has a relationship with a scientific activity, in order to get an understanding that will be given to research materials in the form of objects and subjects, in an effort to have an answer obtained and can be given scientific accountability in the answer including a validity known as a method. While the process is carried out in a systematic way in carrying out analysis and data collection activities in seeking the existence of goals - certain goals to be achieved are definitions for research (Efendi & Ibrahim, 2016: 2-3). In order to realize this research, the method applied is an analytical descriptive method. The purpose of this method is intended to be able to deliver a bright image as a whole, carry out an assessment of the positive norms of the law and dig deeper into the facts of the law. The type of research that is then also applied in this research is normative juridical, all legal materials in the form of various types of regulations that apply in Indonesia are things that are focused on analysis in this study, as well as the main foothold in this study.

C. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Introduction of Limited Liability Company Organizations with Legal Entity Status

As a monodualistic being who states that apart from being an individual or individual being who has a life with his own soul, man is also just a social being whose life cannot be separated from society. In a society' life the relationship between one human being and another is something that happens every day. The relationships that are established between humans are based on interests. With these interests, it often results in humans facing each other or even until there is a resistance. Then, it will result in a riot from these interests (Hajati, et al. 2017:1).

Basically, all human interests in society are always governed by a law. Where the definitions of the law are very diverse and cannot be set out in one definition alone. According to the author of the law is everything that consists of various regulations regarding human life starting from behavior, behavior, and so on, where there are sanctions that will be imposed on violators of these legal regulations. Not only that, but the law is also a regulation that is coercive and binding. In a law, of course, there will be a subject and object of law, where the subject of the law according to the law is something that is given a right and obligation to him and gets authority in carrying out an action.

The subject of law here consists of a human being/individual or individual (natuurlijke person) who is in spiritual health and is not under guardianship. Then it also consists of legal entities (rechts persons). In addition to the next subject is the object of law is everything that can be useful for a legal subject and can be used as a principal in a legal relationship, which is carried out by a legal subject, usually referred to as an object or right that can be owned and controlled

by a legal subject (Tambunan & Wilson. 2019: 9). In the case of legal subjects who are individuals or individuals here can carry out a business activity. Where a business can also be referred to as a company that is an organization that has a business in producing products in the form of goods and services in order to meet customer needs.

A business will not be able to run smoothly if there are no business people behind it. The business actors consist of

- 1) Owner, where this owner consists of a person or more than one person who has capital who then invests in a business, or those who have established a business. Within a predetermined period of time, investors certainly really expect their investments to bear fruit more than the level they have previously invested. Meanwhile, businesses that are run sometimes by other people who are the trust of business owners, but sometimes business owners are also directly involved in realizing all their business activities (Tambunan & Wilson. 2019: 11).
- 2) Creditor, in this case is a financial institution or an individual who provides money loan services. In this case, the creditor provides a lot of capital and is sufficient to lend to the parties who need funds to build their business (Tambunan & Wilson. 2019:11)
- 3) Employee, is someone who earns wages and welfare from the owner of the business where they work. Where these employees have contributed their energy and thoughts to the company or business. Those employees are employed by the company to help operationalize the business.
- 4) The supplier in this case is a party from the external environment of the company that helps the company to obtain raw materials for the smooth operation of their business. Because the company will not be able to provide the materials they need separately, so they will appoint suppliers to send raw materials according to the company's request (Tambunan & Wilson. 2019:11).
- 5) Customers are one of the business people whose position is no less important, because they are consumers where the company will offer all products, both goods and services that will then be enjoyed by them. In order for all consumers to remain subscribed to the company and always use their products, the products produced must be products that have high value and quality (Tambunan & Wilson. 2019: 11).

In realizing a business activity, of course, it is always related to business law. Business law is a set of legal rules which contains regulations regarding procedures and methods regarding the implementation of trade, industrial, or financial affairs or activities that have a relationship with production activities or the exchange of goods and services by providing a place for the placement of money from entrepreneurs in a certain risk with a certain business as well, with a motive that is none other than to reap profits (Tambunan & Wilson. 2019: 20). In a business organization, of course, there will be various forms in it. These forms of business organization will have their own characteristics and the regulations that regulate them are different.

Basically, an organization has legal subjects, both individuals and legal entities. An individual is a company established by a sole proprietor, consisting of only one individual and the individual is fully responsible for the control of the company.

Among the subjects of the law will be several organizations established by them based on laws and regulations, especially Limited Liability Companies. Where a limited company is an organization that stands under a regulation that houses it, namely the Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 40 of 2007 concerning Limited Liability Companies. The definition of a limited liability company from the Act is that what is meant by a limited liability company, which is then a legal material that is a capital partnership, established under an agreement, conducting business activities with an authorized capital that is entirely shared in shares and meets the requirements set forth in this law and its implementing regulations.

Basically, a limited liability company is also known as a form of the existence of a modern corporation, in which three characteristics are expressed, among which are

- a. The nature of ownership of a limited liability company is in the form of shares – shares that can be transferred quickly and easily to be transferred ownership to anyone.
- b. A limited liability company can be said to be a corporation that can live eternally, which means that a limited liability company can remain standing for a long period of time and is not determined by the length of life of the shareholders.
- c. Liability in this case is not only limited to shareholders who are only civil in nature, but there is also liability for criminal acts that are feared to be carried out by the company at any time. Meanwhile, for the administrators, there is also limited liability (Widjaja.2008:11).

There are three sources of capital owned by limited liability companies based on the Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 40 of 2007 concerning Limited Liability Companies, including

- a. Authorized capital

This authorized capital is the capital owned by the company as a whole, which has been included in an articles of association (article 31).

- b. Issued capital

Issued capital is the authorized capital either in whole or in part to which the owner of the capital or shareholders has been allocated (article 33).

- c. Deposit capital

This capital is capital that has been specifically allocated to each capital owner or shareholder who has been fully paid up, so that to carry out operational activities the company can use the capital that has been put into the company's treasury (Tambunan & Wilson. 2019: 20).

The issuance of shares in a company is under the name of the owner of the shares, this is based on articles 48 to 53 in the Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 40 of 2007. To be able to own a share, prospective shareholders generally have to adjust to the ownership requirements in the provisions stated in an articles of association based on the authorized agency that has set these requirements in accordance with the provisions of the laws and regulations.

If the requirements regarding share ownership are not met, then the rights as shareholders of certain parties who have obtained ownership of the shares cannot be realized and the calculations that should be in the shares that should be achieved based on the provisions of the laws and regulations regarding limited liability companies and / or articles of association will no longer be enforced or eliminated. With the establishment of a limited liability company, the legal status separately directly becomes the legal entity status of the company. In this case, the category of legal entity status is to fall into the scope of legal entities, specifically artificial legal entities, which are created by the implementation of a law so that the formation of economic activities, which have similarities with human beings, namely individual people can be realized (Widjaja.2008: 11-12).

Limited Liability within the Scope of a Limited Liability Company

Assets in a limited liability company are assets with separate property status that will be recorded in a separate name and for all actions carried out including the agreement is the responsibility of the company separately. This means that a company can bind themselves to one or more agreements, by making the company an independent subject of law, to which the authority and capacity in court are attached to be able to become plaintiffs and defendants (Widjaja.2008:11-12).

On the other hand, in a Limited Liability Company enacts the principle that a legal entity can be distinguished from a human being. Where humans and legal entities are the two forms of legal entities that together bear rights and obligations, but the existence of responsibility is different. Basically, humans are creatures that are born, have a form, and will eventually come to death. This is different from a Limited Liability Company which is an intangible legal entity which is an artificial person.

Legal entities have a different nature from the nature of human beings as subjects of law. Where a PT is born with a process of establishing a PT, but the PT will never face the name of death as faced by humans who have lives. The life span of an LLC is long or lasting and not limited to time, then the life span of the owner is also not a determinant of the age of a PT.

In order for the purpose and objectives of a pt to be realized, in carrying out legal actions, representatives of the organs in it are needed. So that for legal actions that are needed, the liability of the PT organ will bear this and the principle of limited liability by the PT also applies in it. Basically, in this limited liability company organization, the ownership status has no dependence on a specific individual person, namely the founder of the company or shareholders in the company. At any time, without a predetermined period of time, the existing shares may be freely transferred to anyone in accordance with the provisions of the articles of association and laws enacted at a certain time.

Then the responsibility that will be imposed on the founders as well as for the shareholders is limited. Where the founders and shareholders do not have to bear all the consequences that exist, but are only intended for and only on behalf of the company, even for losses and their own interests.

In principle, a limited liability company will be established on the basis of an agreement. Thus, a pt should be required to meet the elements, principles, and all requirements for the validity of an agreement contained in the Civil Code. With this principle, it is ensured that in order for a PT to be established, the founder should be 2 (two) or more people with an authentic deed from a Notary. If these requirements are not met, there will be consequences that are imposed on the status of liability limited to the Limited Liability Company becoming an indefinite responsibility. The meaning of unlimited liability is that all legal actions up to those that then cause losses in a Limited Liability Company will be directly transferred and charged into the responsibility of the individual shareholders. With this situation, of course, it will be very contradictory to the principle on the word "limited" in limited liability companies that has been in effect so far (Harahap, 2021:10).

The establishment of a Limited Liability Company carried out by an individual person should not be in line with the limited principle, because in its management a Limited Liability Company requires two /more people to be able to control the management. This is important so that the function of "checks and balances" can be implemented or in other words it can be said that the control and balance contained in every decision-making activity is strategic for the Limited Liability Company. Meanwhile, if it is remembered that the principle of liability is limited to a Limited Liability Company, then the requirement of two persons/more is very important so that the limited principle can always be applied and effectively enforced (Harahap, 2021: 10).

The liability of the shareholders of a limited liability company is a characteristic of a limited liability company, but at any time the limited liability of these shareholders may be erased. This occurs if there is evidence of bad faith from the shareholders and the existence of an event of mixing the personal property of the shareholders with the company's property, thus if a limited liability company is only established to be a tool used for the benefit of each individual of the shareholders. Thus, the principle of separate (separation) of PT from shareholders must be separated by means of penetrating the company's veil against the shield of nature limited to liability in certain events (Harahap, 2021: 11).

D. CONCLUSION

Humans over time have become more and more interested in the business world. Various businesses have been carried out including one of which is to establish a company. Where one of the companies that many are established today is a Limited Liability Company. Where to form an LLC requires an agreement between two or more people.

On the other hand, a limited liability company is a legal subject. But basically the subject of law consists of individual persons or individuals and legal entities. Where the PT is entered as

a legal entity. As a legal entity, the age of establishment of a PT is unlimited and is not determined by the period of time, and is not determined by the age of its founder.

The liability of an LLC is limited. Where it is charged against the founders as well as for the shareholders, so they will not bear all the risks that will occur, but only on behalf of the PT and their own interests.

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